

OPTIMIZING THE USE OF COW DUNG ASH IN SUSTAINABLE MORTAR

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the use of cow dung ash (CDA) as a replacement for cement by weight in concrete for the purpose of sustainability. Various weight percentages of CDA cement replacement were evaluated. Compressive strength (in psi) of concrete was found to decrease by 20-25% for 5%, 10%, and 15% CDA replacement samples. Compressive strength decreased by 40% for 20% CDA replacement. Chemical and physical characterization tests were conducted for analysis on the CDA amended cement samples showed that the composition and structural integrity of concrete remained largely unchanged up to 15% CDA cement replacement.

KEYWORDS

Sustainability; concrete; Cow Dung Ash (CDA); supplemental cementitious materials, CO₂, CH₄

INTRODUCTION

Concrete, composed of cement, water, sand, gravel, and rock (Cook, 2015), is one of the most widely used materials in the world (Wangler et al., 2019) for the construction of bridges, buildings, and dams. About 10 km³ of concrete are used per year (Flatt et al., 2012), but according to the International Energy Agency, the cement sector is the third-largest industrial energy consumer and the second-largest global industrial CO₂ emitter due to the use of clinker, the main ingredient in Portland cement (Shalini et al, 2006). Global warming is caused by the emission of greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (NO₂), methane (CH₄) (Al-Ghussain, 2019). Clinker production contributes to about 10% of the total global CO₂ emission (Wangler et al., 2019).

Global cement production is expected to increase by as much as 23% by 2050 as rapid urbanization continues across Southeast Asia and sub-Saharan Africa (International Energy Agency, 2018). This challenge has intensified the search for supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) such as sawdust Ash (SDA) and Rice husk Ash (RHA) (Elinwa, 2003). The literature also suggests the use of cow dung ash (CDA) that can be used as partial cement replacement thereby minimizing the CO₂ emissions and embodied energy usage associated with its production.

In indigenous construction, cow dung has been used for several years in adobe brick production and researchers have investigated the effects of cow dung ash (CDA) in cement paste and concrete (Pavan et al, 2012). The disposal of cow dung, the undigested residue of plant matter which has passed through the animals (cow) gut presents a problem of environmental pollution for communities in several rural parts of Africa. Cow dung is rich in nitrogen, calcium, carbon, potassium, and phosphorus [4] but produces 250 to 500 L of methane (CH₄) per day (Johnson et al, 1995). This will contribute about 2% to global warming in the next 50 to 100 years (Johnson et al, 1995).

The use of CDA amended cement is advantageous to reduce both CO₂ and methane emissions in the atmosphere. CDA's fine particle size has a bearing on its pozzolanic potential when CDA is used as a cement replacement material in mortar production based on biochar obtained synergies with our collaborators in the agricultural sector. This study contributes to the research on cow dung as a cement replacement and provides additional information on the physical and chemical characterization of cow dung ash as well as its effect on the compressive strength and bulk density of cement. The effect of cow dung ash on the microstructure of cement was also evaluated. Finally, recommendations for the appropriate weight percentages of CDA for use were determined.

MATERIALS

Cow Dung Ash

The cow dung cakes used in this study were provided from a private farm in Butte, Montana. Cow dung ash was obtained by burning the cow dung cakes in a Barnstead Thermolyne 6000 furnace at 500°C for 3 hours to calcinate it to ash, crushing the cow dung cakes into a powder using a mortar and pestle and then sieving it through a 300 µm sieve as shown in Figure 1 (Omoniyi et al., 2014). The resultant black colored ash was then stored in an airtight bucket to prevent it from absorbing moisture. The chemical composition of cow dung ash was obtained by Inductively Coupled Plasma Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES). Particle size analysis of the cow dung ash was found using laser diffraction on the Mastersizer 3000.

Figure 1: Preparation of Cow Dung Ash

Mortar Mixture

The mortar mixtures investigated contained Type I/II Portland Cement that meets the requirements outlined by ASTM C 150, fine aggregate that meets the requirements of ASTM C 128 and C 33 with 0.9 Absorption (ABS) and 2.61 Specific Gravity (SpG), and 5%, 10%, 15% and 20% cow dung ash (CDA).

Mix Design

All mortar mixtures were designed based on a water cement ratio (w/c) 0.443 and contained 55% fine aggregate. The control mix design contained cement, fine aggregate, and water. To test the effects of the CDA on the strength of the mortar, four other mix designs were made, substituting CDA in various percentages by weight (5%, 10%, 15% and 20%) to cement. By substituting the CDA for cement *by weight*, the water cement ratio remained constant, allowing for true comparison of the effects of the CDA on the strength of the concrete. The batch weights of the mixtures can be found in Table 1. Control samples contained Type I/II Portland Cement, fine aggregate, water, and no CDA

additions were used for comparison with the CDA amended cement samples in all the tests performed.

In accordance with ASTM C 109 (ASTM C109, 2021), the mortar cubes were cast in a steel mold after mixing. Once casting was completed, the mortar was cured in a humidity room at 23 °C and 95% relative humidity for 7 or 28 days, respectively. Each of the mortar steel molds were 2 inches by 2 inches by 2 inches as shown in Figure 2.

Table 1: Batch weights of Mortar mixtures

Mix #	w/cm	Cement (kg/m ³)	CDA (kg/m ³)	Fine (kg/m ³)	Water (kg/m ³)	Fine Aggregate Type
Control	0.443	1186	0	2842	543	Natural Sand
5% CDA	0.443	1127	59	2842	543	Natural Sand
10% CDA	0.443	1068	118	2842	543	Natural Sand
15% CDA	0.443	1008	181	2842	543	Natural Sand
20% CDA	0.443	950	237	2842	543	Natural Sand

Figure 2: Preparation of Mortar mixtures

METHODS

Ten mortar cubes were prepared to study the effects of adding CDA in various percentages by weight (5%, 10%, 15% and 20%) to Portland cement. The four CDA mixes and control mix samples were allowed a cure time of 7- and 28-day periods. Chemical characterization was done through X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (XRF) and inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES). Physical characterization was done by using scanning electron microscope (SEM) images paired with energy dispersive spectrometry (EDS) for analysis of pore structures on the CDA amended samples (Millogo et al., 2016). Particle size was measured with laser diffraction. Compressive strength cube tests were also performed on the CDA amended samples.

Chemical Characterization

ICP-AES was conducted on a Thermo iCAP 7400 spectrometer, and results were compared to Geological Rock Survey standards as well as Environmental Protection Agency quality control standards. ICP-AES samples were dissolved with a mixture of sodium peroxide flux, before being melted over a Bunsen burner and dissolved in a solution of hydrochloric acid. Samples were subjected to sodium peroxide fusion, as well as acid digestion on a hot plate. Trace element concentrations were reported as oxides by weight percentages in parts per million and compared to rock standards in order to calibrate results. These results were cross referenced with those from XRF testing, to determine elemental composition of samples.

XRF was conducted on each sample using the pellet method, with silver, aluminum, and copper filters, to measure the elemental composition of each of the samples. Metal filters are used to aid in electrical conduction. The samples were made into pellets by mixing them with a binder and pressing them at high pressure (Abdunnabi, 2012). The samples were placed in the Epsilon 1, which is a fully integrated energy dispersive XRF analyzer consisting of a spectrometer, built-in computer, touch screen and analysis software. When a sample is excited by X-rays, it emits characteristic fluorescent X-rays which are used to identify the elements in the sample.

Physical Characterization

Particle size distribution of the CDA was measured by laser diffraction on the Mastersizer 3000. CDA particles were suspended in a 120 milliliter Hydro MV medium, before laser beams of 470 nanometers and 632.8 nanometers were projected through the sample. The angular scattering intensity data was then analyzed to determine the size of particles responsible for the scattering.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) was used to investigate morphological properties of individual particles and the percentage of the elements present. SEM also shows the effect of the CDA on the changing properties of cement (Ramachandran et al, 2015). For SEM imaging, each sample was cut, mounted in epoxy and polished to one micron. A Quanta 250 ESEM microscope was utilized along with a back-scanning detector to produce clear SEM images. SEM imaging was used with EDS to produce the best results.

Electron Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) was used to measure the elemental composition of the samples. EDS analysis was conducted using the X-Act detector from Oxford Instruments and collected at an accelerating voltage of 20 keV. Element, weight percentage, and apparent concentration were determined by measuring the x-ray intensity ratio, k , for each element and applying matrix corrections for any electron backscattering and energy loss. EDS can simultaneously analyze the entire surface under the electron beam and provide qualitative analysis of the major elements on the surface.

Compressive tests of mortar cubes were performed according to ASTM C 109 (ASTM C109, 2021). To perform these tests, cubes were removed from moulds and placed onto the compression strength test machine. Compressive strength tests were performed by placing a load on two cubes of each mortar mix to determine the maximum load at which the cement block fails as shown in Figure 3 (Maguedeswaran et al, 2018), and the average compression strength for each mix was calculated as shown in Table 2. Compressive strength tests were performed after 7 and 28 days of curing. Figure 3 shows the 5% CDA amended samples before and after compressive strength testing.

Figure 3: 5% CDA-amended cement samples after compressive testing

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical Characterization of Cow Dung Ash and Type I/II Portland Cement

ICP-AES Analysis of Cow Dung Ash

Table 2 shows the chemical properties, resulting from the ICP-AES testing of Type I/II Portland Cement and Cow Dung Ash (CDA). The data is provided in weight percentages (parts per million). The chemical composition of Type I/II Portland Cement predominate amounts of calcium oxide (CaO) as well as oxides of potassium (K₂O), aluminum (Al₂O₃), silica (SiO₂), and lower amounts of both magnesium oxide and iron (III) oxide. Also found in the Type I/II Portland Cement are Tricalcium silicate (allite) (C₃S), Dicalcium Silicate (belite) (C₂S), Tricalcium aluminate (C₃A), and Tetra-Calcium aluminoferrite (C₄AF), where C stands for calcium oxide, s for silica, A for alumina, and F for iron oxide (Abdunnabi, 2012). According to Bediako et al. (2015), during cement hydration, CaO along with SiO₂, Al₂O₃, and Fe₂O₃ leads to the formation of calcium aluminosilicates and aluminoferrite hydrates due to cement hardening.

The cow dung ash chemical composition obtained from ICP-AES analysis in Table 2 shows that CDA is composed of considerable amounts of silica oxide as well as oxides of alumina, calcium, potassium, sodium and iron. These chemicals are considered major contributors, making up three to five weight percent of the 30-micron sample; any elements present in quantities ranging from 0.2-3 percent were considered minor or trace contributions. Elements that had the greatest precision when compared to a standard were the Fe₂O₃, Al₂O₃, CaO and SiO₂. These findings describe how the main high-melting components of cow dung ash are silicon and aluminum compounds, while the low-melting components include alkali compounds, among others, potassium, sodium, and organic compounds (Szymajda et al., 2020). The cow dung ICP-AES results confirm what is known in the literature that CDA contains a high amount of silica, a pozzolanic material, which also is advantageous in providing resistance to microbial degradation of cement (Vishwakarma et al., 2016).

The presence of similar chemicals was found in both the Type I/II Portland Cement and cow dung ash samples but in different concentrations. The high amount of silica in the CDA amended cement samples confirms the pozzolanic qualities of CDA and its potential to be used as an amendment material in cement due to its chemical composition similarity.

Table 2: Chemical Composition of Cow Dung and Type I/II Portland Cement

Oxides	Wt %	
	Type I/II	CDA
Al ₂ O ₃	47.00	6.11
BaO	-	0.05
CaO	62.10	3.45
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.60	1.58
K ₂ O	62.10	2.35
MgO	2.40	1.22
MnO	-	0.10
Na ₂ O	0.20	1.07
P ₂ O ₅	-	1.51
SiO ₂	21.10	66.10
SrO	-	0.03
TiO ₂	-	0.24
C ₃ S	57.00	-
C ₂ S	18.00	-
C ₃ A	8.20	-
C ₄ AF	7.80	-

XRF Analyses

The elemental compositions of the samples were measured by X-Ray Fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF). The XRF graphs for the control and 5% cement amendments are shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, as shown in the Appendix. The concentrations were measured in weight percentages (%) and parts per million (ppm). The control samples and CDA amended samples all showed the presence of calcium, silicon, aluminum and iron as major elements in higher percentages and Mg, P, S, K, Ti, Pb and Mn in the lower percentages. Minor elements detected of Cl, V, Cr, Ni, Cu, Zn, Sr and Ba were measured in the parts per million (ppm) range. From Figures 4 and 5 and other additional XRF data, it was shown that as the CDA composition of the concrete increases, the same is true for concentrations of aluminium, iron, and silicon; conversely, calcium composition decreased as more CDA was added (Figure 4 and Figure 5). Through XRF it was shown that calcium, silicon, iron, and aluminum together composed nearly 95% of the sample's mass.

Physical Characterization

Particle Size Analysis of Cow Dung Ash

The surface mean diameter of the CDA was 17.5 μm and its volume mean diameter was 41.1 μm as shown in Figure 6. About 50 wt% of the cow dung ash presented a size lower than 28.4 μm , whereas 90 wt% of the sizes were below 93.6 μm . The particle size distribution of CDA can be found in Figure 6 in the Appendix.

SEM Analyses

The SEM analysis of the control sample and the CDA amended samples after 28 days of curing are shown in Figure 7. The microstructural differences were analyzed in control samples and each CDA amended cement sample. The SEM of the control samples showed particles which were bigger and separated from each other with large spaces between the particles (Millogo et al, 2016). Conversely in Figure 7, the 10% and 20% samples were homogeneous, more connected and had fewer voids between particles (Millogo et al, 2016). This phenomenon was observed with all of the 7-day and 28-day CDA amended samples regardless of the percentage of CDA used. This is believed to be due to the high percentage of SiO₂ found in CDA which serves as a filler material and decreases the space between the particles (Ramachandran et al, 2016).

The weight percentages of the different elements in the control and CDA-amended samples were measured using EDS. The EDS peaks were predominantly comprised of Si, Ca and O as shown in Figure 8. The EDS analyses of cow-dung shows that it also contained alumina, sulphur, phosphorus, calcium, potassium, and iron compounds. The EDS analyses also confirmed that CDA had more silica than the control samples containing only cement.

Figure 8: EDS analyses with 5%, 10%, and 15% CDA composition

Compressive Strength

Compressive strength was tested on the various mortar mixes and the control samples to determine the effect of adding CDA on the strength of cement. The compressive strength results for the control and

CDA-amended cement samples are shown in Figure 9 below. Looking at 7-day average compressive strength (psi) in Table 2, the compressive strength average for the 5% CDA sample drops by 33.0% compared to the control compressive strength average. Similarly, the 10% CDA, 15% CDA, and 20% CDA averages drop by 11.1%, 12.3%, and 34.8% respectively compared to the control 7-day sample. Looking at 28-day average compressive strength (psi) in Table 2, the compressive strength average for the 5% CDA sample drops by 22.6% compared to the control compressive strength average. Similarly, the 10% CDA, 15% CDA, and 20% CDA averages drop by 19.8%, 25.9%, and 40.1% respectively compared to the control 28-day sample. As concrete compressive strength is typically evaluated at 28 days, it can be expected that compressive strength will drop by 20-25% with 5-10% CDA cement replacement. At 20% CDA replacement, concrete compressive strength is expected to drop significantly (by 40%).

Figure 9: Compressive Strengths of Cement Cubes

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results show that cow dung ash can be used as a partial replacement in cement. The chemical composition of CDA obtained through ICP analyses was confirmed through EDS and XRF analyses and showed a high amount of silica, which acts as a filling agent in the cement, as well as calcium, alumina and calcium compounds which are beneficial in cement production. The compressive strength of CDA amended cement samples were evaluated but showed lower compressive strength than Type I/II Portland cement. Based on the results of this study, the following recommendations are suggested:

- (1) CDA can be used as a replacement for cement in concrete up to 15% by weight
- (2) It can be expected that compressive strength will drop by 20-25% with 5-10% CDA cement weight replacement. At 20% CDA weight replacement, concrete compressive strength is expected to drop significantly by 40%.

CITATIONS

Abdunnabi, A. R. (2012). XRF analysis of Portland cement for major and trace elements. *Proceedings of the Eleventh Arab Conference on the Peaceful use of Atomic Energy, Khartoum, Sudan*, 44(26), 1-15.

Al-Ghussain, L. (2019). Global warming: review on driving forces and mitigation. *Environmental Progress and Sustainability Energy*, 38(1), 13-21. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ep.13041>

Bediako, M., & Opoku Amankwah, E. (2015). Analysis of Chemical Composition of Portland Cement in Ghana: A Key to Understand the Behavior of Cement. *Advances in Materials Science and Engineering*. 2015. 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/349401>

Cho, Y.K., Jung, S.H., & Choi, Y.C. (2019). Effects of chemical composition of fly ash on compressive strength of fly ash cement mortar. *Construction and Building Materials* 204, 255-264 . <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.01.208>

Cook, M.D. (2015). *Aggregate Proportioning For Slip Formed Pavements And Flowable Concrete*. OSU Dissertations. <https://hdl.handle.net/11244/45243>

Dhaka, J.K., & Roy, S. (2015). Utilization of fly ash and cow dung ash as partial replacement of cement in concrete. *International Journal Of Civil And Structural Engineering*. 6(1), 36-39. DOI: [10.6088/ijcser.6004](https://doi.org/10.6088/ijcser.6004)

Elinwa, A.U. (2003). Timber Ash as Pozzolana in concrete. Unpublished Doctoral dissertation, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi.

Flatt, R.J., Roussel, N., & Cheeseman, C.R. (2012). Concrete: An eco material that needs to improve. *Journal of European Ceramic Society*, 32(11), 2787-2798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2011.11.012>

International Energy Agency (2018, April). *Cement technology roadmap plots path to cutting CO₂ emissions 24% by 2050*. International Energy Agency. <https://www.iea.org/news/cement-technology-roadmap-plots-path-to-cutting-co2-emissions-24-by-2050>

Johnson, K.A. & Johnson, D.E. (1995). Methane emissions from cattle, *Journal of Animal Science*, 73(8), 2483–2492. <https://doi.org/10.2527/1995.7382483x>

Magudeaswaran, P., & AS, H. (2018). Development of Eco Brick and Concrete with the partially replacement of cow dung. *Development*, 6(5).

Millogo, Y., Aubert, J-E., Séré, A.D., Fabbri, A., & Morel, J-C. (2016). Earth blocks stabilized by cow-dung. *Materials and Structures*, 49(11), 4583- 4594. DOI: 10.1617/s11527-016-0808-6

Omoniyi, T., Duna, S., & Mohammed, A. (2014). Compressive Strength Characteristics of Cow Dung Ash Blended Cement Concrete. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 5(7), 770-776. DOI:[10.14299/ijser.2014.07.003](https://doi.org/10.14299/ijser.2014.07.003)

Pavan, V.S.R, Rayaprolu, K. & Raju, P.P. (2012). “Incorporation of cow dung ash to Mortar and concrete”. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*.2 (3), 580-585.

Ramachandran, D., George, R. P., Vishwakarma, V., Anbarasan, N., Viswanathan, K., Kumari, K., & Venkatachalapathy, V. (2015, December). Studies of strength, durability and microstructural properties of cow dung ash modified concrete. In *2nd RN Raikar Memorial International Conference*

and Banthia-Basheer International Symposium on Advances in Science and Technology of Concrete, vols. 284e291, pp. 18e19 (Mumbai).

Vishwakarma, V., & Ramachandran, D. (2016). Microbial deterioration effect of cow dung ash modified concrete in freshwater environments. *Concrete Research Letters*. 7(3). 84-95.

Shalini, A, Prem,V and Dahiya, R.P(2006). Application of a system dynamics approach for assessment and mitigation of CO2 emissions from cement industry. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 79(2006 Pages 383-398.

Szymajda, A., Laska, G., & Majewski, M. (2020). Characteristics of Ashes from the Combustion of Cow Dung Biomass. *Proceedings*, 51(14), 1-3. <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2020051014>

Wangler, T., Roussel, N., Bos, F.P., Salet, T.A., & Flatt, R.J. (2019). Digital Concrete: A Review. *Cement and Concrete Research*, 123, 105780. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2019.105780>

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

APPENDIX

Figure 4: XRF pattern of the Control (7-day cure)

APPENDIX

Figure 6: Particle size distribution of Cow Dung Ash